

FORMING CULTURE OF WORK PROTECTION IN ENTERPRISES AND ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, the improvement of the state of labor protection in workplaces, the formation of a safety culture, statistics of unfortunate events, and also the scientific proposal and practical recommendations formed by the authors on this issue are expressed in the article.*

Keywords: *labor protection, accidents, safety culture, safety techniques, working conditions, international labor organization.*

Introduction. According to UN figures, the labour that sustains society financially and economically makes up 45% of the world's population, or 7 crore roughly 3 billion people.

Additionally, China (795 million) ranks first globally in terms of the population's level of physical ability (more than), followed by India in second position (500 million, nearly), the European Union in third place (230 million), and Uzbekistan in fourth place (18 million, nearly). Our nation has 14.8 million economically active people, of whom 13.6% work in industry, 29.1% in agriculture, 10.6% in trade, and the rest in other sectors.

Main part. Protecting Republic citizens from the effects of various hazardous and harmful factors that are present or may arise during the production process and in other situations, ensuring their social protection on the basis of laws and other regulatory documents, and establishing working conditions that adhere to sanitary and hygienic requirements are some of the main focuses of social policy in our nation.

These laws aim to protect the health and labor of citizens by establishing a uniform process for arranging labor protection, independent of the mode of production.

The work done by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, today to strengthen national statehood and sovereignty, to ensure the rule of law in society, to uphold the rights and freedoms of our people, to ensure that all citizens are free and equal in all spheres of life, and to pay attention to the nation's future and to everyone who is not indifferent.

With a clear understanding of this, the Ministry of Poverty Reduction and Employment of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been actively working to increase the legal literacy of our citizens, provide for their decent working conditions, and regulate the relationship between employers and employees.

Issues such as consistent increase in employment and real incomes of the population, improvement of social protection and health care system, increase socio-political activity of women are reflected in one of the areas of particular recognition of the new Uzbekistan development strategy for 2022-2026 adopted in our country.

Ensuring the safety of a person during any activity has been and remains one of the important issues from antiquity to the present.

The creation of safe working environments has always received significant attention from humanity. The Greek philosophers Arastu (387–322 BC) and Hippocrates (459–377 BC) were the

first to bring up the topic. The detrimental effects of ore dust on human health were discussed by Hippocrates. He had never previously assembled a list of malevolent works, described the negative effects of using a hookah. A later publication by another scientist contains a thorough description of the pathological conditions brought on by Golen lead dust. The harm caused by the dust that emerges during the extraction of goldsmith was also studied by Pliny the Elder in the first century BC.

The great Uzbek Hakim Abu Ali Ibn Sino founded the discipline of hygiene with his work (980-1087 BC) more than 1000 years ago.

As a result of the rapid development of the field of Mining Metallurgy in the 15th and 16th centuries, scientific work on difficult working conditions, occupational diseases arising as a result of dust in mining went to a lot. It is considered the work of Agricole and Pracelsa.

The great thinkers of antiquity and the middle ages provided the foundation for the development of a distinct discipline that investigates the causes of illnesses linked to occupation. The rightful inventor of science is the Italian doctor Bernadino Ramasini (1633–1714), professor and rector of the University of Padua. His main work, Reflections on the Diseases of Artisans, examines concerns of occupational hygiene in a number of sectors and provides clinical descriptions of diseases associated with particular occupations. For this effort, the scientist compiled more than 50 years' worth of data. He studied the living and working situations of artisans and factory workers as the medieval system gave way to the early stages of capitalism.

Sharp developments are being made in the field of production thanks to scientific and technological advancement. The shape of the weaponry and the labor subject are evolving during this phase. In turn, this is having an impact on working conditions.

The number of workers bidding their lives farewell surged at an unprecedented rate in the mid-1980s in the United States, Canada, several European, and Asian nations due to catastrophic industrial injuries. Major trade union groups in the US and Canada started the "Salvation Day" initiative in 1989 as a way to remember workers who had died.

With support beginning in 2003, the International Labor Organization officially proposed April 28 as the date for the first World Labor Protection Day, which was established in 1996.

Since April 28, 2003, the International Labor Organization has organized the event, which has become a tradition and is now observed in more than 100 countries around the world. The event's goals are to strengthen the global economy's response to a major issue, namely unfortunate victims whose consequences at work are mild, severe, and fatal, prevent occupational diseases, and raise awareness of labor protection issues.

According to the International Labor Organization, every year in the world

More than 300 million unfortunate pilgrims, 160 million occupational diseases are registered, related to production, and due to occupational diseases, there are 2,780,000 female and male crowds, averaging 6,500 people every day, with one crowd every 15 seconds.

As a result of the injury, one-third of employees are harming the economy by not being in the workplace for more than 4 working days.

According to the data, the agriculture sector—where over half of the world's workforce is employed—observes half of the terrible occurrences that occur annually in the workplace.

Each year, 340 thousand workers are in the crowd while under the influence of harmful substances, and 12,000 youngsters are engaged in labor activity at work. One hundred thousand chayotes are being carried solely by asbestos.

Cancer is the third leading cause of mortality from work-related causes, and it can be brought on by asbestos, other carcinogenic powders and chemicals, ionizing radiation, and other factors.

Due to the potential of radiation exposure, 11 million employees worldwide receive medical exams each year. There is one death toll for 5,000 injuries in some of the professions that need first aid.

Cancer is 32% of the leading causes of death associated with labor activity.

Working-related cardiovascular disease and members of the musculoskeletal system together account for about half of the losses.

Those who die as a result of an unfortunate accident and with a strain on production are equal to the number of people suffering from infectious diseases.

According to research, between 50 and 60% of job loss in Europe is associated with production stress.

According to the UN, 45% of the planet's population, almost

The world's labor force, which supports society monetarily and economically, is made up of 3 billion individuals. One billion of the three million workers work in agricultural and small businesses, and 100 million businesses are classified as small businesses.

The International Labor Organization estimates that the loss of 4% of the global economy's gross domestic product due to production-related damage and occupational sickness consequences.

The march of globalization is giving us new tasks. By fostering a healthy workplace where people may work in security, we hope to accomplish that.

Experience has shown that a high security culture benefits everyone—employees, companies, and the general public.

The result of carefully considered policies, social tripartite conversation, community interaction, employer and trade union dialogue, and labor unions is the high demand for labor protection. Additionally, the strengthening of labor protection laws Socks and workplace hygiene are key indicators of the labor inspectorate's (labor protection) active job.

In the majority of developing nations, the core sectors of the economy—agriculture, fishery, construction, forestry, and mining—are affected by ill-wishers and occupational diseases.

An rise in death rates is caused by an inadequate level of employee knowledge, a lack of training in safe working practices, insufficient communication with fire and hazardous materials, as well as an informal economy.

The failure of the head, engineer, technicians, and specialists to carry out the requirements of their position duties, directives, non-compliance, non-compliance with the requirements of labor protection rules and norms, and the deterioration of leadership control by the accountable parties of the relevant officials in this regard are the main causes of accidents.

With a study of working conditions, privileges and guarantees are established in the Republic for employees working in unfavorable working conditions in the manner required by law. These include preferential pensions, lower working hours, more paid time off, free food for treatment and prevention, and high tariff wages.

Conclusion.

The organization's management system must follow certain rules due to the labor protection culture in order for employees to participate in this system. In the age of globalization,

it is guaranteed on a worldwide scale that the country's efforts to strengthen labor protection would succeed without incident.

In the ILO's experience, these obligations arise when the required choices for labor protection are taken in collaboration with three parties, namely employees and employers. These concerns are reflected in the Republic of Uzbekistan's general agreement for 2020–2022.

In organizations that have a management system for labor protection in accordance with the ILO's recommendations, safe and effective labor indicators are expanding. Modern business leaders are aware that improving employee productivity and security is a solid foundation for boosting the organization's competitiveness.

The unquestionable financial comfort of safe labor gives rise to the expectation that compensation for workplace fatalities, illnesses, and injuries will decline. Large organizations are aware that the public receives information about their actions. Recently, projects have started incorporating indicators like labor security, environmental security, and social issues. Production-related injuries and brief absences from the workplace have considerable expenses for the business. There are numerous examples where trustworthy labor protection has a favorable impact on output metrics.

This can also be observed in countries that seek to make progress in the context of globalization.

The inability of individual states to spend funds on labor protection, not meeting labor protection standards, can also contribute to a decrease in competitiveness. But what basis these arguments Hecht does not have.

“It is necessary to pay for security, and for its absence it is paid” (За безопасность необходимо платить, а за ее отсутствие расплачиваться) said Winston Churchill. Labor protection-oriented funding is not an expense, but an investment for the future.

Raising the culture of labor protection prophylaxis to a high level means that the health of working people in the workplace is maintained, occupational disease is minimized, and unhappy workers are taken.

REFERENCES

1. The Labor Protection Act of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. The development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, approved by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-60 of January 28, 2022.
3. (Hygienicheskie vzglyadi Abu Ali Ibn Sina) - Scientific article by Sh. Atabaev, 1978y.
4. International Labour Organization Convention No. 187 on the basics of Occupational Safety and hygiene promotion in 2006.
5. Convention of the International Labor Organization on safety and labor hygiene and the environment of Production No. 155.